

MEDICAL SCIENCES

ASTHMA IN PRESCHOOL CHILDREN. DIAGNOSTIC AND THERAPEUTIC DIFFICULTIES

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Abstract

Asthma is the most common chronic disease in childhood (12-14%) worldwide. Most children with asthma develop symptoms at an early age, but their diagnosis is often delayed, and in other cases, a misdiagnosis of "asthma" is made in young children with "viral wheezing". The diagnosis of asthma in children under 5 years of age is largely difficult due to the wide range of diseases in which there may be persistent or recurrent manifestations of bronchoobstructive syndrome (BOS), including dry cough, "wheezing", shortness of breath and expiratory dyspnea, and the fact that lung function testing is practically impossible, making diagnosis an additional challenge. Therefore, underdiagnosis leads to late diagnosis of asthma and unnecessary use of antibiotic treatment for the so-called "recurrent respiratory infections with bronchial obstruction", and on the other hand, overdiagnosis leads to unnecessary drug prophylaxis of asthma and its associated side effects. The diagnosis of asthma in young children is based largely on recurring symptoms, combined with careful clinical assessment of family history and physical findings with careful consideration of differential diagnosis options. Asthma treatment aims to reduce symptoms and the risk of future complications.

Keywords: Childhood asthma; Diagnosis; Wheezing, under- and over-diagnosis; Differential diagnosis; Treatment.

Abbreviations

BOS – bronchoobstructive syndrome
GERD – gastroesophageal reflux disease
DD – differential diagnosis
OCS – oral corticosteroids
ICS – inhaled corticosteroid
MDD - maximum daily dose
PAAPs – personalized asthma action plans
pMDI – pressured metered-dose inhaler
URTI – upper respiratory tract infection
SABAs – short acting beta2 agonists

Introduction:

Childhood asthma is a heterogeneous disease usually characterized by chronic airway inflammation. This is determined by a history of respiratory symptoms such as wheezing, difficulty breathing, chest tightness, and cough of varying variability, frequency, and intensity, along with variable expiratory airflow obstruction. These variations are often triggered by triggers such as exercise, exposure to an allergen or irritant, weather changes, or viral respiratory infections. Recurrent wheezing occurs in a large proportion of preschool children, always with viral respiratory tract infections, and it is difficult to determine when it is a manifestation of

asthma. A positive family history of allergic disease or the presence of atopy or allergic sensitization provides additional prognostic support, as early allergic sensitization increases the likelihood that a child with wheezing will develop persistent asthma^[3]. Recurrent or persistent wheezing in children under 5 years of age may not be a manifestation of asthma, and confirmatory pulmonary function tests are difficult to perform. The younger the child, the less available the guidelines and/or the benefit of medical advances^{[3][26][27][28]}. The development of national guidelines in many countries is a dynamic process that requires continuous updating^[33]. It appears that previous classifications of wheezing phenotypes (episodic and multi-trigger wheezing; or transient wheezing before age 3, persistent wheezing, and late-onset wheezing) do not identify stable phenotypes and their clinical utility is uncertain. However, emerging studies suggest that more clinically relevant phenotypes will be described and phenotype-directed therapy will be possible.^[3]

DD of asthma in children up to 5 years.

Before making a diagnosis of asthma in this age group, it is important to rule out conditions with symptoms similar to asthma, table 1.^{[1][3]}

Table 1.

Common differential diagnostic possibilities in children up to 5 years

Children up to 5 years old	Recurrent viral infections of the respiratory system; Gastroesophageal reflux; Foreign body aspiration; Persistent bacterial bronchitis; Tracheomalacia; Tuberculosis; Pertussis; Congenital heart disease; Cystic fibrosis; Primary ciliary dyskinesia; "Vascular ring"; Bronchopulmonary dysplasia; Immune deficiency.
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Diagnosis and diagnostic issues.

It is challenging to make a reliable diagnosis of asthma in children under 5 years, as episodic respiratory symptoms such as wheezing and coughing are also common in children without asthma, especially in those aged 0 - 2 years. Due to the difficulties in diagnosing asthma, especially in young children, where objective

examination is not possible, it is important to make decisions for each child individually to avoid over- or undertreatment. In order to aid in the diagnostic process of asthma in preschool children with frequent episodes of "wheezing", prognostic assessments were created - the so-called asthma predictive index (API) and then its modified version (mAPI), which determine which of

these children are at higher risk of developing asthma. Despite the clinical significance of these predictive indices in predicting persistent atopic asthma, their application would lead to under-diagnosis of the disease in wheezing non-atopic children and untimely administration of controller treatment. The Asthma Prediction Index (API) was developed in 2000 using data from the Tucson Children's Respiratory Study to predict the risk of developing asthma in preschool-aged children at school age. The API has been used to screen high-risk groups for asthma^[4] and has shown a sensitivity of 72.2% and specificity of 82.0% for current asthma, respectively, but the index has a high negative predictive value (NPV) of 98.6% and a low positive predictive value (PPV) of 14.1%, respectively. In children under 3 years of age with a positive API, the risk of developing asthma at school age is 77% compared with 3% with a negative API.^[5] A positive API requires at least one major or at least two minor criteria in a young child with three or more episodes of wheezing to date. The major API criteria include: physician-diagnosed asthma in a parent; physician-diagnosed atopic dermatitis. Secondary criteria are "wheezing" not associated with colds; Eosinophils $\geq 4\%$ in the bloodstream; Physician-diagnosed allergic rhinitis. While mAPI is only applicable in young children with four or more episodes of wheezing per year and is positive if there are at least one of major criteria (parental asthma, atopic dermatitis, allergic sensitization to at least one aeroallergen) or two of minor criteria (wheezing unrelated to colds, circulating eosinophils $\geq 4\%$, allergic sensitization to milk, eggs, or peanuts). In a high-risk cohort, a positive mAPI greatly increased future asthma probability (eg, 30% pretest probability to 90% posttest probability). With its more favorable positive posttest probability, the mAPI can aid clinical decision making in assessing future asthma risk for preschool-age children. The mAPI's predictive ability depends heavily on prevalence of asthma in the general population.^{[6][7][8]} One study showed decreased exacerbations, decreased controller medication usage, and increased episode-free days in 2- to 3-year-old children with a positive mAPI treated with inhaled corticosteroids compared with placebo.^[17]

Wheezing Phenotypes.^[3]

Two main classifications of wheezing (called wheezing phenotypes) have been proposed in the past:

1. Symptom-based classification: this is based on whether the child has only episodic wheezing (wheezing for discrete periods of time, often in association with URTI, with no symptoms between episodes) or recurrent wheezing (episodic wheezing with symptoms occurring between these episodes, e.g. during sleep or with triggers such as activity, laughter or crying)

2. Time-based classification: Includes transient wheezing (symptoms begin and end before age 3); persistent wheezing (symptoms begin before age 3 and persist beyond age 6) and late-onset wheezing (symptoms begin after age 3).

Theoretically, phenotyping provides diagnostic and treatment prediction, but this is limited in preschool children due to the limited range of asthma medications available in this age group and the instability of phenotypic classification over time^[10]. Phenotypic classification of young asthmatics by age of onset has failed to demonstrate clinical utility^[3]. In a child with wheezing and signs of increased work of breathing, SABA \pm oral steroids should be administered to assess response and, if there is clear improvement and the child has had similar episodes before, a diagnosis of asthma can be made. If the child has a history of severe exacerbations (requiring oral steroids, emergency department visits, or hospitalization) or frequent symptoms, a trial of daily ICS should be undertaken to determine response, and if the frequency and/or severity of symptoms improves, a diagnosis of asthma may be made.^{[9][10][11][12]}

Any of the following features in a child aged 5 years or younger suggests an alternative diagnosis and indicates the need for further investigation and it is indication for referral for expert advice:^[3]

- Developmental delay
- Neonatal or very early onset of symptoms
- Vomiting associated with respiratory symptoms
- Persistent wheezing despite bronchodilator use
- Lack of response to asthma medications (ICS, oral steroids, or SABA)
- Lack of association of symptoms with typical triggers, such as viral URTI
- Focal pulmonary or cardiovascular signs, or "drumstick" fingers and nail or (digital) clubbing
- Hypoxemia outside the context of a viral illness.

According to GINA, the symptoms/signs that suggest asthma in children up to 5 years of age are listed in table 2. A diagnosis of asthma in young children with "wheezing" is very likely if they have: Wheezing or coughing that occurs with exercise, laughter or crying, or in the absence of an obvious viral infection; History of allergic disease (eczema, allergic rhinitis), allergen sensitization or asthma in close relatives; Clinical improvement during 2–3 months of controller treatment with low-dose ICS plus, as needed, SABA as a reliever and worsening when these medicines are stopped; Exclusion of an alternative diagnosis.

Table 2

Signs/symptoms suggestive of asthma in children ≤ 5 years.

Symptom	Features suggestive of asthma
Cough	Recurrent or persistent nonproductive cough that may be worse at night or accompanied by wheezing and difficulty breathing. It occurs with exercise, laughter, crying, or exposure to tobacco smoke in the absence of a respiratory infection.
Wheezing	Recurrent wheezing, including during sleep or from triggers such as activity, laughter, crying, or exposure to tobacco smoke or polluted air.
Difficulty breathing or shortness of breath	Occurs during exercise, laughter, or crying.
Decreased activity	The child does not run, play, or laugh with the same intensity as other children; gets tired earlier while walking (wants to be carried).
Past or family history	Other allergic diseases (atopic dermatitis or allergic rhinitis). Asthma in first-degree relatives.
Trial of low-dose ICS and, when necessary, SABA treatment	Clinical improvement after 2-3 months of maintenance treatment and deterioration after its discontinuation.

Exacerbations of asthma in preschool children.

An asthma exacerbation in children aged 5 years and younger is defined as an acute or subacute worsening of symptom control sufficient to cause distress or risk to health and to require a visit to a healthcare professional or retreatment with systemic corticosteroids.

Early symptoms of an acute asthma attack in young children include: Worsening of symptoms;

Worsening of cough, especially at night; Lethargy or decreased exercise tolerance; Decreased daytime activity, including eating; Poor response to reliever medications.

Determining the severity of an asthma exacerbation.

The characteristics that determine the severity of an exacerbation are present in table 3. [3]

Table 3

Initial determination of acute asthma attack in children up to 5 years

Symptom	Mild	Severe *
Changes in consciousness	No	Excited, unable to speak, confused, or sleepy
Oximetry at baseline (SaO ₂)	>95%	<92%
Conversation with sentences/words	Sentences	Words
Can he/she drink liquids?	Yes	NO
Pulse rate	<100/мин.	>180 (0-3 год.) >150 (4-5 год.)
Respiratory rate	≤ 40/минута	> 40/минута
Central cyanosis	Absent	Often present
Wheezing intensity	Variable	May be absent/silent lung on auscultation

*Each of these signs is an indication for immediate hospitalization of the child.

In addition to the signs above, indications for immediate hospital admission are any one of the following:

- Lack of response to 6 puffs of inhaled albuterol (salbutamol) - 2 separate puffs, repeated 3 times over 1 - 2 hours

- Persistent tachypnea*, despite three consecutive puffs of inhaled SABA, even if the child shows other clinical signs of improvement

- Social factors in the child's environment that prevent parents from treating the child at home

* Normal respiratory rate: < 60/min for children up to 2 months of age, < 50/min for children 2-12 months of age, < 40/min for children 1-5 years of age.

Treatment.

The goals of asthma management in young children are to achieve good control of symptoms and maintain normal activities, minimize risk of exacerbations, and minimize side effects from medications. The Global Initiative for Asthma (GINA) offered a stepwise

approach to treatment that is customized to the individual child taking into account the effectiveness of available medications, their safety, and their cost to the payer or family. The need for additional controller treatment should be re-evaluated at each visit and maintained as short as possible taking into account potential risks and benefit. If the asthma diagnosis is confirmed and factors that hinder response to the previous step are excluded, further elevation of ICS dose is considered with monitoring for side effects^{[3][13][25]}. Other options include the addition of regular LTRA after considering the risk-benefit.^[25]

The ultimate goal of modifying the natural course of the disease is unattainable with currently available medications. According to GINA recommendations, the decision to initiate daily controller therapy depends on the frequency, severity, and duration of symptoms, along with clinical manifestations and family history of atopy^{[3][14]}. Treatment with ICS is associated with a lower risk of relapses, fewer hospitalizations, and a re-

duced need of reliever as β 2-agonists^[15-16]. ICS are recommended for children with persistent symptoms or who have received 2 or more courses of systemic corticosteroids within a 6-month period, as they have been shown to reduce the severity of exacerbations by 35%^[17]. However, it is increasingly recognized that the heterogeneity of wheezing in early childhood is associated with different patterns of airway inflammation and that ICS are not an effective treatment for every phenotype^[18-20]. The combination of sensitization to inhaled allergens and peripheral blood eosinophilia >300 cells/ μ l has been shown to predict a positive response to ICS^[21]. Although allergen sensitization is a marker of a steroid-sensitive phenotype, the majority of preschool-aged children with asthma (approximately 75%) are non-atopic and require a different therapeutic approach.^[22]

Choosing the appropriate device.

Inhaled therapy is the cornerstone of childhood asthma management. Choosing the appropriate device

is considered to be as important as choosing the medication, as proper handling of inhalers is essential to ensure that patients receive the prescribed dose. Inspiratory flows and lung volumes are largely dependent on height and increase with age and body mass, so many children will not be able to generate sufficient inspiratory flow to properly use an inhaler device by the age of 5 – 6 years. The preferred route of administration recommended by GINA is a pMDI administered via a spacer, with a face mask for children up to 3 years of age and without a face mask for those aged 4–5 years.^[23] pMDI - method of administration allows more of the medication to reach the lungs in a shorter time, but requires coordination between inhalation and actuation of the inhaler, and the use of a spacer eliminates this need. Nebulizers are considered a reliable, easy-to-use, and effective alternative to pMDIs, inhalation takes 5–8 minutes and allows the drug to be used by patients of all ages, but with less deposition – about 10% of the aerosol therapy reaches the lungs, table 4^[3]^[24]

Table 4.

The strategy for choosing an inhaler device depending on age.

Age group	Recommended device	Alternative device
0 – 3 years	pMD with corresponding spacer with face mask	Nebulizer with face mask
4 - 5 years	pMDI with corresponding mouthpiece spacer	pMDI with appropriate spacer with face mask or nebulizer with mouthpiece or face mask

Effective asthma management involves a comprehensive approach aimed at both pharmacological and non-pharmacological control. The latter includes education on how to undertake effective treatment, avoidance of triggers, modifiable risk factors and actions to be taken during acute attacks through personalized asthma action plans (PAAP), consideration of the cost of treatment, patient preferences and treatment of comorbidities (chronic rhino-sinusitis, GERD, etc.) and last but not least at each stage of treatment, if asthma control is not maintained, the patient should be monitored for therapy and inhaler treatment technique. PAAPs have been shown to reduce emergency room visits and increase caregiver confidence in managing asthma attacks.^[48]

Pharmacotherapy.

Pharmacological treatment includes two main groups of medications (medications to relieve acute symptoms and medications to control asthma).

1. **Quick-relief medications** to relieve acute asthma symptoms such as wheezing, chest tightness, and coughing during exacerbations of childhood asthma. This group includes:

- SABAs in adequate doses are the drug of choice, especially in children up to 5 years of age. The inhaler route of administration is preferred.^{[3][15-40]}

- Inhaled muscarinic receptor antagonists (IMA), also called M – cholinolytics. IMA are competitive antagonists of acetylcholine versus muscarinic receptors, so they selectively reduce or eliminate parasympathetic stimulation, therefore reducing bronchial spasm, bronchial mucus secretion, and inhibiting bronchial expectoration. This group of medications falls

into two subgroups: short-acting (SAMA) and long-acting (LAMA) muscarinic antagonists. SAMA (main representative is Ipratropium bromide) are the second important group of drugs that are recommended for pharmacological control as inhaled bronchodilators in asthma and are mainly recommended in patients who either do not tolerate or have an insufficient effect of SABA treatment. Ipratropium bromide usually used in combination with SABA in severe exacerbation of asthma.^[41-45]

- Systemic corticosteroids. Systemic corticosteroids do not cause rapid bronchodilation, but nevertheless they are used in view of their strong anti-inflammatory effect for the treatment of more severe asthmatic exacerbations.

2. **Asthma maintenance medications.** These are used daily for a long time to achieve and maintain asthma control and include:

- Leukotriene receptor antagonists (LTRA). LTRA include montelukast and zafirlukast.

- **Inhaled and systemic corticoids.** Corticosteroids, especially ICS, are agents of first choice for the maintenance treatment of asthma. Corticosteroids have a powerful anti-inflammatory effect, reduce bronchial hyper-reactivity, mucus secretion and swelling of mucous membranes, increase the number of beta – adrenergic receptors in the lungs and increase their sensitivity to the action of β 2-agonists. The use of oral or systemic corticosteroids increases the risk of fractures^[46,40]. It is recommended to check the height of asthmatic children treated with ICS at least once a year (GINA 2018). ICS reduce symptoms, exacerbations and prevent airway remodeling, reduce mortality and morbidity in asthma. Initial treatment in children under

5 years of age should begin with a low dose of inhaled corticosteroid. This should be continued for at least 3 months, during which time its effectiveness in achieving symptom control can be assessed. If this is not achieved, the dose should be doubled. The addition of LARA to the initial low dose may also be considered.

Low doses of ICS provide the most clinical benefit for most children with asthma, but higher doses are associated with an increased risk of side effects. Daily low doses of ICS for children under 5 years of age are given in table 5. [47] [3]

Table 5.

Low daily doses of inhaled corticosteroids for children up to 5 years of age.*

ICS	Low daily doses (Age in years)
Beclomethasone dipropionate (pMDI, standard particle)	100 µg (≥ 5)
Beclomethasone dipropionate (pMDI, extrafine particle)	50 µg (≥ 5)
Budesonide (nebules)	500 µg (≥ 1)
Mometasone furoate (pMDI, standard particle)	100 µg (≥ 5)
Fluticasone propionate (pMDI, standard particle)	50 µg (≥ 4)

* This is not a clinical dose equivalence table.

NICE^[12] provides recommendations for the treatment of preschool children with suspected or confirmed asthma or with asthma symptoms that are not controlled by their current treatment. This guidance includes the following steps:

- SABA as reliever therapy for children under 5 years of age with suspected asthma.
- Consider an 8-week trial of paediatric moderate-dose ICS in children under 5 years of age with symptoms at presentation that clearly indicate the need for maintenance therapy (for example, asthma-related symptoms 3 times a week or more or causing nighttime awakenings) or suspected asthma that is not controlled with SABA alone.
- After 8 weeks, stop ICS and continue to monitor the child's symptoms. If symptoms do not resolve during the trial period, review whether an alternative diagnosis is likely. If symptoms resolve and then recur within 4 weeks of stopping ICS, restart paediatric low-dose ICS as first-line maintenance therapy. If symptoms resolve but reappear 4 weeks after stopping ICS, repeat the 8-week pediatric moderate-dose ICS trial.
- If suspected asthma is not controlled in children under 5 years of age on pediatric low-dose ICS and LTRA as maintenance therapy, stop LTRA and refer

the child to a healthcare professional for further evaluation and treatment.

The 2024 GINA Core Report adopted and updated the steps for asthma management proposed in previous reports for children under 5 years of age, table 6.

Step 1: As-needed inhaled short-acting beta2-agonist (SABA). Alternatively, intermittent short-course ICS at onset of viral illness.

Step 2: Initial treatment with controller plus SABA as-needed. Diagnostic trial with daily maintenance ICS for 3 months. Alternatively, daily LTRA or intermittent short-course ICS at onset of viral illness. The adverse effects of montelukast on sleep and behavior in children should be considered, especially since the FDA requires a warning about this.

Step 3: For children whose symptoms are not controlled after 3 months of low-dose ICS, doubling the initial dose is often the best option and re-evaluating after 3 months. Another option is to add an LTRA to low-dose ICS. The FDA warning should be considered. This and the next step should be preceded by excluding other diagnoses, checking inhaler techniques, and adherence and controlling environmental factors, such as exposure to tobacco smoke.

Step 4: Continue controller treatment and refer for expert evaluation.

Table 6.

Stepwise personalized asthma management for children up to 5 years to control symptoms and minimize future risk.

If the patients has:	Steps	Preferred controller options	Other controller options
Asthma not well – controlled on double-dose ICS	4	Continue controller and refer for specialist assessment	Add LTRA, or increase ICS frequency, or add intermittent ICS
Asthma diagnosis, and asthma not well – controlled on low dose ICS	3	Double low dose ICS	Low dose ICS + LTRA Consider specialist referral
Symptom pattern no consistent with asthma but wheezing episodes requiring SABA occur frequently, e.g. ≥ 3 per year or in the case of a symptom pattern consistent with asthma, and symptoms are not well controlled or ≥ 3 per year.	2	Daily low dose ICS	Daily LTRA or intermittent short course ICS at onset of viral illness. Consider specialist referral.
Infrequent viral wheezing and no or few interval symptoms	1	Insufficient evidence for daily controller	Consider intermittent short course ICS at onset of viral illness

Treatment of asthma exacerbations in children up to 5 years.

- The implementation of one or another step depends on the setting where the treatment is carried out: at home, in an outpatient or hospital setting, or in an intensive care unit.
- Parents/caregivers of young children with asthma should be given a written asthma action plan (PAAP) so that they can recognize an impending severe asthma attack, what medication to start treatment with and when urgent hospital treatment is required.
- Initial treatment at home should be with SABA: two puffs (200 µg salbutamol) and observation, re-assessment after 1 hour or less. Medical attention

should be sought if the child is in acute distress, lethargic, unresponsive to initial bronchodilator therapy or worsening, especially in children under 1 year of age. Medical attention should be sought the same day if SABA is required more frequently than 3 hours or for more than 24 hours.

- Treatment of an asthma attack in the emergency department or emergency room. The severity of the exacerbation should be assessed first, while initiating treatment with SABA (2 - 6 puffs every 20 minutes for the first hour) and oxygen (to maintain oxygen saturation 94 - 98%). Treatment of an acute asthmatic attack in children up to 5 years of age is presented in the table 7.

Table 7.

Initial treatment of acute asthma attack in children up to 5 years of age

Therapy	Dosage and method of administration
Supportive oxygen therapy	Delivery by nasal cannula/face mask at a concentration to maintain O ₂ saturation > 94%
SABA	2 puffs of salbutamol (albuterol) metered-dose aerosol with spacer or 2.5-5 mg by nebulizer every 20 minutes for 1 hour*, then reassess severity. If symptoms persist or recur, give an additional 2-3 puffs per hour. Admit to hospital if > 10 puffs are required in 3-4 hours.
Ipratropium bromide in children with moderate - severe exacerbations with poor response to initial SABA administration	1-2 puffs with pMDI and spacer every 20 minutes or 250 µg, with nebulizer every 20 minutes for the first hour only
Magnesium sulfate	Consider nebulized isotonic magnesium sulfate (150 mg) 3 doses within the first hour of treatment for children ≥ 2 years of age with severe exacerbation
Systemic corticosteroids	Oral prednisolone (1-2 mg/kg daily) or intravenous methylprednisolone (1 mg/kg every 6 hours on the first day; every 12 hours from the second day) - up to MDD : 20 mg for children up to 2 years; 30 mg for children from 2 to 5 years . A 3-5 day course is sufficient for all ages and can be stopped suddenly
Intravenous β ₂ agonist	If inhalation is not possible, an intravenous bolus of terbutaline 2 mcg/kg over 5 minutes followed by a continuous infusion of 5 mcg/kg/hour can be administered. (Evidence C). The child should be monitored closely and the dose should be adjusted according to clinical improvement and side effects.

Indications for discharge from the emergency department or hospital after treatment for an asthma exacerbation include: The child's condition should be stable (e.g., able to get out of bed, eat and drink without difficulty) and the need for reliever medication should be no more than 4 puffs of SABA.

Follow-up after an asthma exacerbation.

Before the child is discharged from the emergency department or hospital, the necessary medications (SABA and, when necessary, OCS, ICS or LTRA) should be provided and the family/caregivers should be given the following advice and information:

- ✓ Instructions on recognizing the signs of an asthma exacerbation and worsening and identifying the factors that precipitated the exacerbation and implementing strategies to avoid these factors in the future
- ✓ A written, individualized action plan, including details of available emergency services
- ✓ Careful assessment of inhalation technique
- ✓ The need for early follow-up after an exacerbation. That is, children who have experienced an asthma attack are at risk of further exacerbations, so

follow-up is necessary within 1-2 days after treatment of the exacerbation in the emergency department(ED) or after discharge from hospital and again 1-2 months later to plan or adjust ongoing asthma treatment.

GINA recommends that when determining asthma control, risk factors for poor asthma outcomes in children aged ≤5 years should also be identified.

Gina assessment of asthma control in children 5 years and younger.

- Recent symptom control. In the past 4 weeks, has the child had :
 - Daytime asthma symptoms for more than a few minutes, more than a once a week
 - Any activity limitation due to asthma
 - SABA reliever medication needed more than once a week (excludes reliever taken before exercise)
 - Any night waking or coughing due to asthma
 And in case, the presence of:
 - None of the above, indicates good control
 - 1 – 2 indicates partially controlled asthma
 - 3 – 4 is an indication that asthma is uncontrolled.

Risk factors for poor asthma outcomes in children ≤ 5 years.

a. Risk factors for exacerbations in the next few months:

- Uncontrolled asthma symptoms
- One or more severe exacerbation (ED attendance, hospitalization or course of OCS) in previous year
- The start of the child's usual 'flare-up' season (especially if autumn)
 - Exposures: tobacco smoke; indoor or outdoor air pollution; indoor allergens (e.g. house dust mite, cockroach, pets, mold), especially in combination with viral infection
 - Major psychological or socio-economic problems for child or family
 - Poor adherence with controller medication, or incorrect inhaler technique
 - Outdoor pollution (NO₂ and particles)

b. Risk factors for fixed airflow limitation

- Severe asthma with several hospitalizations
- History of bronchiolitis

Risk factors for medication side-effects

- Systemic: Frequent courses of OCS; high-dose and/or potent ICS
- Local: moderate/high-dose or potent ICS; incorrect inhaler technique; failure to protect skin or eyes when using ICS by nebulizer or spacer with face mask.

Stepping up or down maintenance treatment according to the response.

□ The degree of symptom control, regardless of the current regimen, informs whether changes in maintenance treatment should be made.

□ Asthma control should be reviewed after 6 - 12 weeks and in case of poor control, the following steps are recommended:

- Always check correctness of technique and adherence before proceeding to the next step of treatment
- Consider alternative diagnoses
- Consider increasing the dose if indicated

□ Good asthma control for approximately 3 months suggests that maintenance treatment can be reduced, and it is recommended to continue with the lowest dose that controls symptoms. And to discontinue maintenance treatment only after a period of 3 months without symptoms and to reassess 4 - 6 weeks after stopping it.

□ Consider ongoing management of triggers and seasonal factors when increasing or decreasing treatment.

□ Education that includes: assess parents/caregivers' knowledge and understanding and address gaps, symptom recognition and management, explain the role of reliever and maintenance treatment, proper use of inhaler technique, how to manage emergencies and when to seek medical attention;

□ Recommend annual flu vaccine

□ Check compliance at each visit and address barriers

□ All children should have a written home and childcare action plan. ^{[3][34-39]}

Conclusion.

Given the frequent cases of under- and over-diagnosis in children up to 5 years of age, it is extremely important to first exclude alternative diagnoses and to make decisions for each child individually in order to avoid over- or under-treatment, respectively. Also, before making a diagnosis of "viral wheezing" or "recurrent respiratory infections with BOS" or "asthma", as well as before starting control treatment for "asthma", consultation with a pediatric pulmonologist or a specialist in the treatment of allergic diseases and asthma in particular is recommended. In this regard, we also recommend avoiding frequent prescription of antimicrobials for the treatment of so-called "recurrent/persistent respiratory infections" and unnecessary prescription of a second antibiotic with the justification of "lack of microbial sensitivity or presence of microbial resistance", and instead referring unclear cases to a specialist for diagnostic clarification.

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